

IOT BASED BABY MONITORING SYSTEM FOR SMART CRADLE

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ABSTRACT

This paper is centered around a plan to develop a IOT based Smart baby cradle that would assist the Parents with monitoring and keeping an eye on their infants regardless of whether they are at home or at work and can identify each activity of the infants from any inaccessible corner of the world. It is a brilliant, imaginative and defensive Cradle System to support a newborn child in a productive manner. This framework considers all the moment subtleties that are needed for the consideration and insurance of the Baby in the support. The plan of keenness and development accompanies the utilization of advancements which incorporate Internet of Things (IOT), Modules like Raspberry Pi, Gas sensor, sound sensor and Temperature sensor, Cry Detecting Mechanism, camera surveillance, and much more. To recognize each and every movement of Baby, various Sensors are connected to the Cradle: Gas & Temperature Sensing Module for discovery of wetness of the cradle. A Camera is fitted in the top Cradle for live video film & sound sensor to break down Cry Patterns. All the information which is being taken from the sensors will be put away in information base & recognized at normal stretches. Using all those data and images, parents can be sure about the safety and well being of their babies at any time in any given place.

INTRODUCTION

As we are very well acquainted with the obstacles faced by parents to sustain their baby and particularly in the event that if both the parents are working, to give 24 hours of time in such cases is close to incomprehensible [6]. Along these lines, we ought to create something special that can assist parents with having a consistent observation/watch on the Baby/Infant and can advise about the equivalent. Accordingly, we thought of a plan to plan a Smart Cradle System utilizing IOT which will assist the parents with observing their infant regardless of whether they are far away from home and can identify each action of the infant with any distant corner of the world. It is an imaginative, shrewd and defensive Cradle System to nurture a baby in a proficient manner. This framework considers all the moment subtleties that are needed for the consideration and assurance of the Baby in the support. The plan of quickness and advancement accompanies the utilization of innovations/procedures which incorporate Internet of Things (IOT) technology. Modules like Camera Arduino, Raspberry Pi, Humidity and Temperature sensors, Swing Automation, Cry Detecting Mechanism, Live Video Surveillance, Data Storage and sending of data to the parents through mail. To identify each and every movement of the Baby, various Sensors/Modules are

connected to the Cradle: Humidity and Temperature Sensing Module for identification of Wetness of cradle. A Camera on top of the Cradle for live surveillance and Sound sensor to examine cry patterns which then triggers the swinging system (whenever required) [7]. All the information are taken from the sensors will be put away in Cloud and mailed to the parents at normal spans. All sensor data are combined to get data about the body conditions which is useful as any ordinary manifestations of an illness and can be distinguished without any problem. A moment versatile warning that will be created if any strange movement is recognized (something abnormal like crying of infant or wetness because of Baby Urine) and parent will be notified through mail. The system will be designed such that swinging mechanism of the cradle will be enabled automatically if any abnormal activity is detected.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Oliveira-Jr, K. Cardoso, F. Sousa, and W. Moreira, “A Lightweight Slice-Based Quality of Service Manager for IoT,” *IoT*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 49-75, Aug. 2020.

Industry 4.0 and digital farming rely on modern communication and computation technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) to provide smart manufacturing and farming systems. Having in mind a scenario with a high number of heterogeneous connected devices, with varying technologies and characteristics, the deployment of Industry 4.0 and digital farming solutions faces innovative challenges in different domains (e.g., communications, security, quality of service). Concepts such as network slicing and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) provide the means for faster, simpler, scalable and flexible solutions in order to

serve a wide range of applications with different Quality-of-Service (QoS) requirements. Hence, this paper proposes a lightweight slice-based QoS manager for non-3GPP IoT focusing on different use cases and their varying requirements and characteristics. Our focus in this work is on non-3GPP IoT unlicensed wireless technologies and not specifically the end-to-end network slice perspective as described in 5G standards. We implemented and evaluated different QoS models in distinct scenarios in a real experimental environment in order to illustrate the potential of the proposed solution. : Industry 4.0 and digital farming rely on modern communication and computation technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) to provide smart manufacturing and farming systems. Having in mind a scenario with a high number of heterogeneous connected devices, with varying technologies and characteristics, the deployment of Industry 4.0 and digital farming solutions faces innovative challenges in different domains (e.g., communications, security, quality of service). Concepts such as network slicing and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) provide the means for faster, simpler, scalable and flexible solutions in order to serve a wide range of applications with different Quality-of-Service (QoS) requirements.

H. Chegini, R. K. Naha, A. Mahanti, and P. Thulasiraman, “Process Automation in an IoT-Fog-Cloud Ecosystem: A Survey and Taxonomy,” *IoT*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 92-118, Feb. 2021.

The number of IoT sensors and physical objects accommodated on the Internet is increasing day by day, and traditional Cloud Computing would not be able to host IoT data because of its high latency. Being challenged

of processing all IoT big data on Cloud facilities, there is not enough study on automating components to deal with the big data and real-time tasks in the IoT–Fog–Cloud ecosystem. For instance, designing automatic data transfer from the fog layer to cloud layer, which contains enormous distributed devices is challenging. Considering fog as the supporting processing layer, dealing with decentralized devices in the IoT and fog layer leads us to think of other automatic mechanisms to manage the existing heterogeneity. The big data and heterogeneity challenges also motivated us to design other automatic components for Fog resiliency, which we address as the third challenge in the ecosystem. Fog resiliency makes the processing of IoT tasks independent to the Cloud layer. This survey aims to review, study, and analyze the automatic functions as a taxonomy to help researchers, who are implementing methods and algorithms for different IoT applications. We demonstrated the automatic functions through our research in accordance to each challenge. The study also discusses and suggests automating the tasks, methods, and processes of the ecosystem that still process the data manually. Connecting various objects to the Internet has created a significant shift in the informationbased economy. The flow of information will play a crucial role in future Information Technology (IT) ecosystems [1]. The connectivity of different types of objects, sensors, and end devices to the Internet is known as the Internet of Things (IoT). The expected large number of sensors connecting to the Internet will cause severe issues for IoT task management, data process, and decision-making systems. Because providing the same services to the users will face latency in data management and data processing of IoT

sensors. Therefore, ensuring a good Quality-of-Service (QoS) with a low-latency resolution for IoT applications, IT services, user tasks, and client events in the ecosystem is crucial to support latency-aware real-time applications.

H and U. K, “Cooperative Spectrum Handovers in Cognitive Radio Networks,” EAI/Springer Innovations in Communication and Computing, pp. 47-63, Jul. 2018. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-91002-4_3.

Rapid spectrum usage in wireless networks may reduce energy efficiency, requiring cognitive radio networks to be more efficient than conventional ones. Due to increased data transmission demand, cognitive radio networks arose from a lack of spectrum bandwidth. Spectrum sensing and handoff decision are two cognitive radio network strategies that help avoid interference, channel access, and cohabitation between primary and secondary users. Current research focuses on handoff decision and cooperative spectrum sensing to improve sensing efficiency and system throughput while neglecting energy efficiency and handoff latency. Spectrum mobility and sensing are essential for energy-efficient cognitive radio networks. This study provides a second priority user transmission system using cooperative spectrum sensing to sense available channels. An energy detection technique optimizes the sensing process’s energy usage, leading to energy efficiency. A primary user traffic pattern-based threshold approach is presented for spectrum mobility management. A threshold approach is utilized to calculate probabilistic stay-andwait and QoS handoff values. The transmission channel is selected using a hybrid handoff strategy based on dynamic

spectrum aggregation. Moreover, a cooperative spectrum sensing algorithm is described and simulated to identify the optimum channel with the greatest throughput and minimum energy consumption. The proposed approach increases energy efficiency and throughput while maintaining handoff delay and avoids miss-detection and false alarm. This technique improves energy efficiency, sensing performance, throughput, and handoff time. miss-detection. The rapid growth of wireless applications frequently increases requests for higher information rates, putting the spectrum's fixed properties and allocation policies to the test. To effectively improve static spectrum usage policies, the advantageous attribute of Cognitive Radio (CR) has been established based on the dynamic spectrum. Cognitive radio is one of the promising techniques that prominently resolve the spectrum scarcity issue by optimizing the spectrum.

Aziz, O. Schelen, and U. Bodin, "A Study on Industrial IoT for the Mining Industry: Synthesized Architecture and Open Research Directions," *IoT*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 529-550, Dec. 2020.

The Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) has the potential to improve the production and business processes by enabling the extraction of valuable information from industrial processes. The mining industry, however, is rather traditional and somewhat slow to change due to infrastructural limitations in communication, data management, storage, and exchange of information. Most research efforts so far on applying IIoT in the mining industry focus on specific concerns such as ventilation monitoring, accident analysis, fleet and personnel management, tailing dam monitoring, and pre-alarm system while an

overall IIoT architecture suitable for the general conditions in the mining industry is still missing. This article analyzes the current state of Information Technology in the mining sector and identifies a major challenge of vertical fragmentation due to the technological variety of various systems and devices offered by different vendors, preventing interoperability, data distribution, and the exchange of information securely between devices and systems. Based on guidelines and practices from the major IIoT standards, a high-level IIoT architecture suitable for the mining industry is then synthesized and presented, addressing the identified challenges and enabling smart mines by automation, interoperable systems, data distribution, and real-time visibility of the mining status. Remote controlling, data processing, and interoperability techniques of the architecture evolve all stages of mining from prospecting to reclamation. The adoption of such IIoT architecture in the mining industry offers safer mine site for workers, predictable mining operations, interoperable environment for both traditional and modern systems and devices, automation to reduce human intervention, and enables underground surveillance by converging operational technology (OT) and information technology (IT).

H. Anandakumar and K. Umamaheswari, "A bio-inspired swarm intelligence technique for social aware cognitive radio handovers," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 71, pp. 925-937, Oct. 2018.

doi:10.1016/j.compeleceng.2017.09.016.

A novel dynamic spectrum sharing method inspired by natural communities based on social language has been proposed to overcome prevailing spectrum

underutilization and scarcity. The Social Cognitive Radio Network (SCRN) combines social data and mobile communication network by providing a range of data delivery services concerning social relationship among mobile users. The research focuses on diverse SCRN applications and its handover issues, a bio-intelligent supervised learning approach called SpecPSO is devised for performing social cognitive handover (SCH) to:. Experimental results show that the proposed SCH-SpecPSO outperforms 75% more than state of art mobile social networks by optimizing various handover issues. Next generation of wireless networks will largely depend on cognitive radio technology which offers high performance communication networks. The entire radio spectrum is segregated into two divisions, the licensed frequency and unlicensed frequency. The primary users make use of the licensed spectrum exclusively and that includes ultra high frequency/very high frequency [1] bands. The rapidly growing demand towards the wireless communication technology creates a huge burden on the available insufficient wireless spectrum. The way to mitigate this unavailability of spectrum space is to incorporate cognitive radio (CR) technique over these wireless technologies. Both the network communication and the data must be closely connected to each other. Both network and data communication needs to be closely interlinked in order to emphasize effective connection between people and the communication device. Earlier researches have involved into all aspects of CR including spectrum access and open spectrum auction with the [2] dynamic spectrum rental. The cognitive radio social network focuses on data transmission issues faced commonly. It is a way of unaware learning where the information acquired is inaccessible to the perceiver's knowledge and control. This is not because of the physical

properties of the stimuli (such as subliminal exposure time), but due to the relative slowness and inefficiency of the human perception. The cognitive engine (CE) makes the decision in changing its own functionality.

EXISTING SYSTEM

Normally, baby cradles are used in numerous hospitals and parenthood for parents and caretakers to get relieve and take rest. Basically in remote places the cradles are manually swung and require manpower and they also accept these ordinary cradles because of its low price and ease. These cradles are not automated and do not require electric power. Therefore, conventional cradles have to be automated to provide greater help, safety and security to the infants as well as the people monitoring them. Hence, research has been done on how to bring automation in this area while not compromising the safety and security of the infants as they are very soft and tender by nature. Few researches have investigated the possibilities of automatic child cradle in unique ways [9]. A toddler integrated tracking has been proposed which decreases sound pollutants has been recommended. The primary function of the match built integrated is to lessen the noise that might disturb the toddler integrated by us built integrated builtintegrated relaxing songs. This built-in integrated can also regulate the room's mild depth integrated with the resource of a light sensor. however, our device has greater superior features, together with built-integrated real-time surveillance using IOT and visual monitoring integrated built-internet digital camera. Goyal and Kumar introduced an automated baby cradle ,which will detect if the baby cries and starts swinging the cradle until the baby stops crying .

PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this proposed framework, three sensors namely Gas sensor (MQ-135), Temperature sensor (LM-35), Sound sensor (KY038) and anticipating cloud is utilized, so that subsequent information having high precision about the infant's condition can be obtained. Additionally, we are obtaining live images of the youngsters through camera module through a Wide Area Network (WAN). Motors are also present which enable the swinging mechanism. In this task MCP3008 is utilized, so as to associate 3.3v pin from raspberry pi to all sensors. Similarly, MCP3008 and all sensor's ground pins ought to be grounded. Now interface sensor's yield pins to each station of MCP3008 (ex: LM-35 to station 0, GAS to station 1 and SOUND sensor to station 2 of MCP3008). Connect USB camera with raspberry pi0. Also connect the motors using the motor driver to Raspberry pi. Connect power supply for Raspberry pi. Plug the HDMI link in Raspberry pi from the screen using VGA to HDMI converter link. Connect USB Mouse and USB console

Block diagram

RASBERRY-PI

Raspberry Pi is a small single board computer. By connecting peripherals like

Keyboard, mouse, display to the Raspberry Pi, it will act as a mini personal computer.

Raspberry Pi is popularly used for real time Image/Video Processing, IoT based applications and Robotics applications.

Raspberry Pi is slower than laptop or desktop but is still a computer which can provide all the expected features or abilities, at a low power consumption.

Raspberry Pi Foundation officially provides Debian based Raspbian OS. Also, they provide NOOBS OS for Raspberry Pi. We can install several Third-Party versions of OS like Ubuntu, Archlinux, RISC OS, Windows 10 IOT Core, etc.

Raspbian OS is official Operating System available for free to use. This OS is efficiently optimized to use with Raspberry Pi. Raspbian have GUI which includes tools for Browsing, Python programming, office, games, etc.

We should use SD card (minimum 8 GB recommended) to store the OS (operating System).

Raspberry Pi is more than computer as it provides access to the on-chip hardware i.e. GPIOs for developing an application. By accessing GPIO, we can connect devices like LED, motors, sensors, etc and can control them too.

It has ARM based Broadcom Processor SoC along with on-chip GPU (Graphics Processing Unit).

SOUND SENSOR

A sound sensor is defined as a module that detects sound waves through its intensity and converting it to electrical signals. But do you know how sound sensor work? What it is used for? and How to pair a sound sensor with Arduino? Fear not, with today's guide, I'll be answering all of these questions!

Based on the power amplifier LM386, the Grove – sound sensor module is a simple, low powered, and highly compatible option suitable to easily kickstart your next sound sensing project!

With a wide voltage range and adjustable output by the potentiometer, it's readily capable to detect the sound strength of the environment!

Its features include:

- [Grove](#) compatible interface
 - Seeed's own plug and play system, no soldering or jumper wires needed for pairing as compared to other sound sensor breakout boards
- Analog output signal
- Wide supply voltage range: 4V-12V
- Low quiescent current drain: 4mA
- 2.0cm x 2.0cm twig module
- Minimum external parts

DC WATER PUMP

Micro DC 3-6V Micro Submersible Pump
Mini water pump For Fountain Garden Mini water circulation System DIY project. This is a low cost, small size Submersible Pump Motor which can be operated from a 3 ~ 6V power supply. It can take up to 120 liters per hour with very low current consumption of 220mA. Just connect tube pipe to the motor

outlet, submerge it in water and power it. Make sure that the water level is always higher than the motor. Dry run may damage the motor due to heating and it will also produce noise.

BUZZERS

In common parlance a Buzzer is a signaling device that is not a loudspeaker. It can be mechanical, electromechanical, or electronic (a piezo transducer). BeStar produces Buzzers in every available configuration for a wide variety of applications. A Piezo transducer can produce the sound for panel mount buzzers, household goods, medical devices and even very loud sirens. When a lower frequency is required an electromagnetic buzzer can fill the need. These are very common in automotive chimes and higher end clinical diagnostic devices. The BeStar buzzer range includes self drive units with their own drive circuitry (indicators), or external drive units, which allow the designer the flexibility to create their own sound patterns.

CONCLUSION

Our proposed framework targets observing the indispensable indications of the child, for example, pulses and internal heat level utilizing remote innovation and sound sensor used to quantify infant cry's. We additionally center around increment the extent of sending the data over the web to give far off access.

The camera module consolidated empowers showing the visual feeds of the whereabouts of the child and keeping an eye over their developments in a limited territory. This framework defeats the disadvantage of the current frameworks which are awkward, less easy to use and costly.

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